

**COGNITIVE AND PRAGMATIC ASPECTS OF
MEDIA LINGUISTICS**

Xaitova Lobar Azamatovna

QDU magistranti lingvistika (ingliz tili)

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mediatilshunoslik hamda uning kognitiv va pragmatik jihatlari haqida fikr va mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Tilshunoslik, lingvistika, kognitiv, pragmatik, til, kognitiv tilshunoslik, media tarmoq, OAV.

Abstract. This article presents thoughts and comments about media linguistics and its cognitive and pragmatic aspects.

Key words. Linguistics, linguistics, cognitive, pragmatic, language, cognitive linguistics, media network, mass media.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены мысли и комментарии о медиалингвистике и ее когнитивных и прагматических аспектах.

Ключевые слова. Лингвистика, лингвистика, когнитивный, прагматический, язык, когнитивная лингвистика, медиасеть, средства массовой информации

The field of linguistics is the most necessary part of the society, and as the language develops, so does the society. The field of linguistics has a very ancient history, and its study began in ancient India. There are many subfields of linguistics, and in this article we want to focus on pragmatics and cognitive linguistics. Not long ago, the term cognitive linguistics entered the field of linguistics. Therefore, it is no exaggeration to say that it is one of the most pressing issues of modern linguistics today. It is worth noting that the interaction between language and consciousness, problems, connections, the importance and role of language in conceptualizing and categorizing the world, and in cognitive processes based on human experience, in order to generalize with the individual cognitive abilities of a person, that is, understanding and understanding is a new linguistics that studies the relationship between language and their mutual influence and its forms.

Cognitive linguistics is also complicated because it studies concepts and linguistics closely. Because the concept is different for each individual and it is based on the environment in which he grew up. Cognitive linguistics has been officially studied as a separate field since 1989. This year, a conference was first organized in the German state of Duisburg within the framework of cognitive linguistics. The participants of this symposium formed the International Association for Cognitive Linguistics, and since then the interest and research in cognitive linguistics has increased. In cognitive linguistics, we see a new stage in the study of the complex relationship between language and thought, a problem that is mainly characteristic of Russian theoretical linguistics.

As an independent direction in modern linguistics, the formation and development of media linguistics depends on a number of factors related to both linguistic and information technologies and socio-cultural spheres of social life. The mass media is considered as the authority of the public environment, and especially the mass media language has been studied as a tool with social power. Language is a transparent phenomenon. The media often claim neutrality,

thereby creating an environment for reflecting public opinion and reflecting the opinions and judgments and arguments of newsmakers.

One of the most important conditions for the emergence of medially linguistics is the following.

- In particular, the rapid growth of information and communication technologies (ICT), manifested in the creation of a global media network;

- formation and development of a single information space as a new virtual environment of text communication; - formation and scientific understanding of the concept of "media language", determining its functional and stylistic features and internal structure;

- to realize the need for a comprehensive approach to the study of speech in mass media, based on the joint efforts of representatives of various humanities;

- consideration of media language learning within media studies

- a new independent science, the topic of which is a comprehensive analysis of the historical development, current state and characteristics of the entire mass communication complex.

Undoubtedly, the concept of media text, noted in all works devoted to the production of speech in mass media, is an important theoretical component of media linguistics. The essence of this concept can be summarized as follows: in traditional linguistics, the meaning of the text can be defined as "the coherent and mutual integrity of spoken and written language". In the media text, the person thinks about the world as a real reality, and this thinking is recorded in a verbal-non-verbal form similar to the characteristics of a person's perception of the world and his thinking. It is this situation that justifies the need to move from the research based on the principle of "thing in itself" from within the linguistic units to the search for the "base point" that allows studying the media communication language as a functional whole from the outside. The analysis of linguistic phenomena allows to clearly define what role language plays in the process of media communication only if it is carried out together with extra-linguistic phenomena.

Thus, the media text is not only a product of mass media: the active trend of modern mass media is the saturation and integration of information at the intersection of journalism, computer technologies, advertising and PR, social networks, etc. Scholars of various fields are thinking about its interpretation: grammar, text linguistics, medially linguistics, psycholinguistics, etc. Accordingly, today we have different approaches to studying the text.

Speaking about the main features of the use of language in the mass media, researchers have noted that the influence of mass speech on modern speech is very large and requires careful, systematic study. A detailed study of some media languages led to the expansion of the concept of "media language", which in turn was reflected in the separation of the oral and media or audiovisual levels. On the other hand, considering the language of mass media as a mixed type of sign system that combines verbal and audiovisual codes made it possible to determine the linguistic characteristics of each specific mass media. Finally, a characteristic feature of the language of print media is the interaction of its verbal and graphic components. The type and size of the font, the presence of images, the use of colors, the quality of the paper, the arrangement of the material in the lines - all this is closely related to the line of words and forms a single unit - the syncretic language of the press.

Cognitive and pragmatic aspects of modern media linguistics occupy a great place in our cultural life.

The cognitive aspect describes the learning tools of receiving, recording and analyzing information in the process of communication and information acquisition through media linguistics. This aspect expresses the variability of media linguistics, including structural and structural-decreasing information.

Pragmatic aspect, in media linguistics, describes people's communication with themselves, conveying messages to other people, language, and including methods of conveying messages in the process of communication, appropriateness of language to the context, relationships between personalities. This aspect explains the connection of media linguistics with social, economic and political problems and tasks.

Cognitive and pragmatic aspects of modern media linguistics provide insight into human relationships, spirituality, activities and thought processes. In these aspects, media linguistics has an important impact on changes in our spirituality and cultural life.

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